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The impact of negative affect and emotional distress on executive functions in breast cancer patients

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Introduction: Breast cancer is a disease which is often followed by unpleasant patients' emotional states and emotional distress, especially when the situation is uncertain and when important decisions about further treatment are to be made. On the other hand, negative emotions can significantly interfere with the process of decision making and proper following of the protocols of treatment in such ways in which they, as it is assumed, influence the work of executive functions because they both rely on overlapping brain networks. The aim of this study is to examine whether the trait negative affect and distress contribute to the difficulties in different domains of executive functions in breast cancer patients.

Material and methods: The research was designed as a cross-sectional study in which 32 patients (Mean age=57,18 ± 12,06 SD years) were examined prior to their chemotherapy treatment at the Institute for Oncology of Vojvodina, Serbia. The Trait Negative Affect was measured with the SIAB-PANAS, total score of DASS- 21 was used as a measure of distress, while the assessment of daily behavior belonging to specific aspects of executive functions was investigated with the BRIEF- A. After controlling age and education ($p > .05$), a couple of regression analyses were conducted, with the negative affect and distress being predictor variables and different domains of executive functions being criterion ones.

Results: The negative affect ($\beta=0,319$; $p < 0.05$) and distress ($\beta=0,412$; $p < 0.05$) proved to be significant predictors of global executive functioning and explained 31,8% variance $F(2,29)=8,215$; $p < 0,001$. The observation of the specific domains showed the significance of distress in prediction of Inhibition ($\beta=0,375$; $p < 0.05$) where it explains the 12,5% of the variance $F(2,29)=4,199$ $p < 0.05$, the Working Memory ($\beta=0,384$; $p < 0.05$) in which it explains the 13% of variance $F(2,29)=3,299$ $p < 0.05$, the Organisation of Materials ($\beta=0,446$; $p < 0.05$), in which it explains the 17,6% of variance $F(2,29)=4,171$; $p < 0.05$, the Shift ($\beta=0,384$; $p < 0.05$) to which it gives contribution of 13% of variance $F(2,29)=4,505$; $p < 0.05$, as well as the Task monitor domain ($\beta=0,347$; $p = 0.05$), there by giving a single contribution of 10,6% $F(2,29)=4,387$; $p < 0.05$. Plan/Organize domain was explained by both predictors in the model with 28,7% variance $F(2,29)=5,837$; $p < 0.01$, where the only significant contribution is the one of the negative affect ($\beta=0,373$; $p < 0.05$). Emotional control was significantly predicted and explained with 18,8% variance $F(1,30)=6,935$; $p < 0.05$ by the negative affect as a single predictor variable ($\beta=0,433$; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: The findings indicate a considerable importance of the negative emotions in the explanation of the executive functioning difficulties in breast cancer patients. There is vulnerability for the manifestation of the deficits within the ones that show an increase in the trait negative affect, and the vulnerability is increased even more within the ones experiencing emotional distress. The above mentioned implies the significance of adequate recognition and treatment of the emotional distress and investigation of the other factors which can additionally affect the executive functions of the patients because preserved executive functions are the base for cooperation during the treatment and thus significantly contribute to better quality of life in patients.

Keywords: cancer, affect, distress, executive functions, psychooncology